

Facile cleavage of vicinal tertiary diols by pyridinium dichromate

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Vicinal tertiary diols with diaxial hydroxyl groups are cleaved selectively by PDC (pyridinium dichromate) under mild conditions to give the corresponding diketones in high yields.

Oxidative cleavage of a diol is one of the most important transformations in organic synthesis. Conventionally this is performed by periodic acid¹, sodium periodate² and lead tetracetate³. Activated-manganese dioxide⁴, thallium nitrate⁵, xenic acid⁶ and pyridinium chlorochromate⁷ are also effective reagents for this reaction. Although there are literature precedents for glycol oxidative cleavage reactions, there appears to be no report for selective PDC oxidation of a diaxial tertiary diol.

Scheme 1

Oxidation of triol **1** with excess PDC (10 eq.), gave diketone **2**, instead of the expected ketone **3**, as the sole product in 93% yield (Scheme 1). The stereochemistry of the secondary hydroxyl in **2** is α -form from its coupling constant. Even though the reaction time was increased to 19 h using 10 equivalent of PDC, the corresponding triketone **4** was not produced.

Similarly, MOM ethers **5** and **6** bearing vicinal diaxial tertiary hydroxyl groups were converted into the corresponding diketones **7** and **8** in quantitative yields, respectively, as shown in Scheme 2.

Interestingly, when triols **9** and **10** were subjected to PDC oxidation, the spectral data (¹H, ¹³C NMR) showed that the

Scheme 2

product **11** from both **9** and **10** were identical (Scheme 3). Furthermore, the MOM derivative of compound **11** was found to be identical to compound **8** by ¹H NMR. The absolute configuration of **11** was determined from the ¹H NMR of its MTPA^{8,9} ester.

Scheme 3

The mechanism of oxidative cleavage of vicinal tertiary diols in compounds **1**, **5** and **6** probably follows the classic pyridinium chlorochromate reaction⁷ mechanism. However, for triols **9** and **10**, it is unusual that diastereomers are converted into the same product. A reaction mechanism in which the stereochemistry of the secondary hydroxyl group is controlled is presented below.

A possible reaction mechanism for the conversion of **9** and **10** into **11** is presented in Scheme 4. Triols **9** and **10** are

oxidized to intermediate **A**, the side-chain carbonyl of which undergoes intramolecular attack of the ester group in unstable tricyclic intermediate **B**. A concerted intramolecular ring cleavage reaction then takes place in intermediate **B** to yield diketone **11** as the single isomer in high yield. The stereochemistry of the secondary hydroxyl group produced by this reaction mechanism is identical with that of **11** based on results of MTPA ester analysis. This reaction implies that the selective oxidative cleavage of vicinal tertiary diols is accompanied by remote asymmetric induction, i.e. steps **A** → **B** → **11**. The reason that triketone **13** is not produced is presumably due to the stabilized conformation **C** of **11** with a sterically hindered hydroxyl group.

Scheme 4

Experimental

^1H NMR spectra were obtained on a Bruker DMX 400 instrument and the residual protic solvent (CDCl_3) was used as an internal reference. ^{13}C NMR was recorded at 75 MHz on a Bruker DMX 400 instrument. Low-resolution mass spectra (EIMS) were measured on a JEOL JMS-600H instrument with an ionization potential of 70 eV. High-resolution mass spectra (HREIMS) were measured on a HITACHI M80-B instrument.

1-Allyl-3 α -methyl-octahydroindene-1,7,7'-triol (1): The triol **1** was synthesized from methyl (*s*)-(-)-methyl-2-oxocyclohexane propionate in six steps. A SmI_2 solution (0.1 M in THF; 100 ml) was added to a solution of (*s*)-(-)-methyl-2-oxocyclohexane propionate (400 mg, 2.02 mmol) in THF (20 ml) at room temperature. After being stirred for 3 h, the reaction mixture was quenched with

MeOH (*ca.* 10 ml). The suspended reactant was filtered by celite and concentrated. The residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (40 : 1 hexanes/EtOAc), affording 3 α -methyl-octahydroindene-1-one (ketone; 264 mg, 86%): ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.06–1.14 (1H, m), 1.20 (3H, s), 1.22–1.29 (1H, m), 1.34–1.52 (5H, complex), 1.63 (1H, dt, J 12.9, 9.8 Hz), 1.80 (1H, ddd, J 12.0, 7.0, 5.2 Hz), 1.86 (1H, br t, J 1.8 Hz), 1.96–2.25 (1H, m), 2.28–2.32 (2H, complex); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 21.30 (t), 21.96 (t), 23.14 (t), 26.22 (q), 34.02 (t), 34.65 (t), 35.39 (t), 38.67 (s), 56.18 (d), 220.70 (s); HRMS found m/z 152.1206 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}$ 152.1201.

An isopropenyl acetate (15 ml) solution of the above ketone (264 mg, 1.74 mmol) including catalytic amount of camphorsulfonic acid (CSA) was heated at refluxing temperature overnight (*ca.* 10 h). The reactant was concentrated and the residue purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (40 : 1, hexanes/EtOAc), affording acetic acid 3 α -methyl-3,3',4,5,6,7-hexahydro-2*H*-inden-1-yl ester (acetate; 324 mg, 96%): ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.10 (3H, s), 1.13–1.36 (3H, complex), 1.47–1.61 (2H, complex), 1.67–1.82 (5H, complex), 2.15 (3H, s), 2.25–2.38 (2H, complex), 2.61 (1H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 21.19 (q), 22.07 (t), 22.87 (t), 23.54 (q), 26.75 (t), 29.31 (t), 38.32 (t), 41.86 (t), 43.26 (s), 131.74 (s), 140.11 (s), 169.17 (s); HRMS found m/z 194.1300 (M^+); calcd for $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{19}\text{O}_2$ 194.1307.

A mixture of the acetate (324 mg, 1.67 mmol), NMO (2.0 g, 17.1 mmol), OsO_4 (2.5 w/% in $t\text{BuOH}$, 0.5 ml) and 80% aqueous acetone was stirred at ambient temperature overnight (*ca.* 10 h). The mixture was then poured into aqueous solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (4 : 1, hexanes/EtOAc), affording 7-hydroxy-3 α -methyl-octahydroindene-1-one (alcohol; 266 mg, 95%): ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 0.92 (3H, s), 1.33–1.36 (1H, complex), 1.42–1.64 (8H, complex), 2.05 (1H, ddd, J 15.5, 9.8, 2.4 Hz), 2.24 (1H, br s, OH), 2.29–2.48 (2H, complex); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 21.15 (t), 21.65 (t), 22.81 (q), 28.15 (t), 31.03 (t), 31.51 (t), 33.29 (t), 40.85 (s), 80.71 (s), 220.35 (s); HRMS found m/z 168.1148 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ 168.1150.

A solution of the alcohol (266 mg, 1.59 mmol) in toluene was heated at refluxing temperature in presence of CSA (5 mg, 0.02 mmol) overnight (*ca.* 10 h). The reactant was concentrated and the residue purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (10 : 1, hexanes/EtOAc), affording 3 α -

methyl-2,3,3',4,5,6-hexahydroinden-1-one (enone, 224 mg, 94%) : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.12 (3H, s), 1.27–1.34 (1H, m), 1.58 (1H, ddd, J 15.6, 12.4, 8.9 Hz), 1.74–1.80 (2H, complex), 1.90 (1H, dt, J 12.5, 3.4 Hz), 2.00 (1H, dd, J 12.2, 8.7 Hz), 2.19–2.34 (3H, complex), 2.47 (1H, ddd, J 18.8, 12.2, 8.7 Hz), 6.61 (1H, t, J 3.7 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 18.65 (t), 25.18 (q), 25.69 (t), 35.70 (t), 36.44 (t), 36.58 (t), 38.84 (s), 132.06 (d), 145.89 (s), 207.64 (s); HRMS found m/z 150.1049 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}$ 150.1045.

A mixture of the enone (224 mg, 1.49 mmol), NMO (1.8 g, 15.4 mmol), OsO_4 (2.5 w% in $^t\text{BuOH}$, 0.5 ml) and 80% aqueous acetone was stirred at ambient temperature overnight (*ca.* 10 h). The mixture was poured into aqueous solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (2 : 1 hexanes/ EtOAc), affording 7,7'-dihydroxy-3 α -methyl-octahydroinden-1-one (diol; 261 mg, 95%) : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 0.92 (3H, s), 1.44–1.64 (5H, complex), 1.65–1.81 (2H, complex), 2.08–2.29 (1H, m), 2.27 (1H, br d, J 8.0 Hz, OH), 2.35 (1H, ddd, J 19.9, 9.5, 1.1 Hz), 2.53 (1H, ddd, J 19.9, 10.5, 2.3 Hz), 3.14 (1H, br s, OH), 3.72 (1H, ddd, J 11.1, 8.0, 4.1 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 20.15 (t), 23.75 (q), 26.72 (t), 29.22 (t), 31.32 (t), 32.18 (t), 41.93 (s), 68.65 (d), 83.11 (s), 218.60 (s); HRMS found m/z 184.1090 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ 184.1099.

A 2.0 *M* solution of allylmagnesium chloride in THF (3.6 ml, 7.2 mmol) was added to a solution of the diol (261 mg, 1.42 mmol) in THF (15 ml) at -78° . The reaction mixture was stirred for 15 min, then at ambient temperature for 3 h. The reactant was quenched with water (*ca.* 5 ml). The mixture was poured into water and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (2 : 1, hexanes/ EtOAc , and then 1 : 1, hexanes/ EtOAc), affording triol **1** (302 mg, 94%) : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.17 (3H, s), 1.32–1.98 (10H, complex), 2.40–2.56 (3H, complex, including OH), 2.66 (1H, br s, OH), 3.30 (1H, br s, OH), 3.55–3.63 (1H, m), 5.19 (1H, br d, J 15.7 Hz), 5.12 (1H, br d, J 7.6 Hz), 5.92–6.02 (1H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 19.54 (t), 25.94 (q), 31.43 (t), 32.39 (t), 34.89 (t), 35.32 (t), 44.46 (t), 45.53 (s), 69.81 (d), 82.10 (s), 82.21 (s), 119.87 (t), 135.32 (d); HRMS found m/z 226.1566 (M^+); calcd for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$ 226.1569.

6-Hydroxy-2-methyl-2-(3-oxohex-5-enyl)cyclohexanone (**2**) : A mixture of triol **1** (20 mg, 0.088 mmol),

PDC (333 mg, 0.885 mmol) and anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (5 ml) was stirred at ambient temperature for 4 h. The mixture was then poured into water and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (4 : 1, hexanes/ EtOAc), affording diketone **2** (18.5 mg, 93%) : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.08 (3H, s), 1.43–1.73 (4H, complex), 1.89–2.08 (2H, complex), 2.12–2.24 (2H, complex), 2.42–2.51 (2H, complex), 3.17 (2H, br d, J 7.0 Hz), 3.68 (1H, d, J 3.8 Hz, OH), 4.35 (1H, ddd, J 12.4, 6.8, 3.8 Hz), 5.16 (1H, br dd, J 17.0, 1.1 Hz), 5.21 (1H, br dd, J 10.2, 1.1 Hz), 5.90 (1H, ddt, J 17.0, 10.2, 7.0 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 19.25 (t), 22.26 (q), 31.17 (t), 36.96 (t), 37.47 (t), 41.30 (t), 48.01 (s), 48.31 (t), 72.98 (d), 119.66 (t), 130.56 (d), 207.78 (s), 215.87 (s); HRMS found m/z 224.1418 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_3$ 224.1412.

1-(2-Hydroxypent-4-ynyl)-3 α -methyl-octahydroindene-1,7-diols (**9** and **10**) : The triols **9** and **10** were synthesized from the previous alcohol (7-hydroxy-3 α -methyl-octahydroinden-1-one) in three steps. A 2.0 *M* solution of allylmagnesium chloride in THF (2.2 ml, 4.4 mmol) was added to a solution of the alcohol (150 mg, 0.89 mmol) in THF (7 ml) at -78° . The reaction mixture was stirred for 15 min, then at ambient temperature for 3 h. The reactant was quenched with water (*ca.* 5 ml). The mixture was poured into water and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (4 : 1, hexanes/ EtOAc), affording 1-allyl-3 α -methyl-octahydroindene-1,7-diol (diol; 180 mg, 96%) : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.11 (3H, s), 1.27–1.66 (7H, complex), 1.71–1.96 (3H, complex), 2.28 (2H, d, J 7.3 Hz), 2.41 (1H, br s, OH), 2.44 (1H, d, J 1.1 Hz, OH), 5.13–5.23 (2H, complex), 5.89–6.03 (1H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 22.07 (t), 22.12 (t), 26.10 (q), 31.15 (t), 32.46 (t), 34.77 (t), 35.25 (t), 42.39 (t), 44.09 (s), 80.66 (s), 81.80 (s), 119.88 (t), 134.80 (d); HRMS found m/z 208.1459 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2$ 208.1463.

A mixture of the diol (180 mg, 0.86 mmol), mCPBA (670 mg, 4.3 mmol) and anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (15 ml) was stirred at ambient temperature for 2 h. The mixture was then poured into aqueous solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (2 : 1, hexanes/ EtOAc), affording separable diastereoisomer (3 α -methyl-1-oxiranylmethyl-octahydroindene-1,7-diol,

polar epoxide 77 mg, 40%, less polar epoxide 117 mg, 60%). Polar epoxide : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.13 (3H, d, J 0.4 Hz), 1.26–1.65 (10H, complex), 1.71–1.83 (2H, complex), 1.92 (1H, dd, J 10.7, 3.4 Hz), 1.97–2.04 (1H, m), 2.52 (1H, dd, J 4.9, 2.9 Hz), 2.56 (1H, br s, OH), 2.81 (1H, dd, J 4.9, 4.1 Hz), 3.01 (1H, br s, OH), 3.28–3.33 (1H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 21.93 (t), 22.08 (t), 26.20 (q), 31.33 (t), 32.68 (t), 35.08 (t), 35.23 (t), 39.83 (t), 43.86 (s), 47.34 (t), 50.32 (d), 80.84 (s), 83.29 (s); HRMS found m/z 226.1565 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$ 226.1569. Less polar epoxide : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.15 (3H, s), 1.32–1.62 (10H, complex), 1.73–1.86 (2H, complex), 1.95 (1H, dd, J 14.3, 3.3 Hz), 2.04–2.14 (1H, m), 2.56 (1H, dd, J 4.8, 2.8 Hz), 2.67 (1H, br s, OH), 2.86 (1H, dd, J 4.8, 4.3 Hz), 3.20–3.25 (1H, m), 3.39 (1H, br s, OH); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 22.04 (t), 26.40 (q), 31.27 (t), 32.96 (t), 34.61 (t), 35.35 (t), 39.04 (t), 43.79 (s), 47.86 (t), 50.38 (d), 80.42 (s), 83.46 (s); HRMS found m/z 226.1565 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$ 226.1569.

A mixture of the polar epoxide (77 mg, 0.34 mmol), lithium acetylide ethylenediamine complex (156 mg, 1.7 mmol) and anhydrous DMSO (8 ml) was stirred at ambient temperature for 4 h. It was then poured into water and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (4 : 1, hexanes/ EtOAc), affording 1-(2-hydroxypent-4-ynyl)-3 α -methyl-octahydroindene-1,7-diol (**9**; 86 mg, quant.) : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.11 (3H, s), 1.24–1.84 (12H, complex), 1.90–2.09 (2H, m), 2.08 (1H, t, J 2.6 Hz), 2.36 (1H, d, J 2.6 Hz), 2.38 (1H, d, J 2.6 Hz), 2.83 (1H, br s, OH), 3.25 (1H, br s, OH), 4.41–4.70 (1H, m), 4.48 (1H, br s, OH); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 21.99 (t), 22.23 (t), 26.04 (q), 28.77 (t), 30.99 (t), 32.37 (t), 35.20 (t), 37.17 (t), 41.93 (t), 44.45 (s), 68.37 (d), 71.53 (d), 80.78 (s), 81.18 (s), 83.53 (s); HRMS found m/z 252.1720 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3$ 252.1725.

A mixture of the less polar epoxide (117 mg, 0.52 mmol), lithium acetylide ethylenediamine complex (240 mg, 2.6 mmol) and anhydrous DMSO (10 ml) was stirred at ambient temperature for 4 h. It was then poured into water and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (4 : 1, hexanes/ EtOAc), affording 1-(2-hydroxypent-4-ynyl)-3 α -methyl-octahydroindene-1,7-diol (**10**; 131 mg, quant.) : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.13 (3H, s), 1.24–1.81 (13H, complex), 2.05–2.12 (1H, m), 2.08 (1H, t, J 2.6 Hz), 2.39 (1H, dd, J 2.6, 1.3 Hz), 2.41 (1H, dd, J 2.6, 1.5 Hz), 2.86 (1H, br s, OH), 3.83 (1H, br s,

OH), 3.94 (1H, br s, OH), 4.10–4.21 (1H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 21.97 (t), 21.97 (t), 26.43 (q), 28.54 (t), 31.43 (t), 32.81 (t), 34.55 (t), 35.41 (t), 41.19 (t), 43.98 (s), 68.78 (d), 71.41 (d), 80.64 (s), 81.04 (s), 84.11 (s); HRMS found m/z 252.1728 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_3$ 252.1725.

1-(2-Methoxymethoxypent-4-ynyl)-3 α -methyl-octahydroindene-1,7-diol (**5**) : A mixture of triol **9** (86 mg, 0.34 mmol), chloromethyl methyl ether (0.05 ml, 0.66 mmol), diisopropyl ethylamine (0.5 ml) and anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (10 ml) was stirred at ambient temperature overnight (*ca.* 10 h). It was then poured into water and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (4 : 1, hexanes/ EtOAc), affording methoxy methyl ether **5** (95 mg, 94%) : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.11 (3H, s), 1.21–1.48 (5H, complex), 1.50–1.57 (3H, complex), 1.61–2.07 (6H, complex), 2.04 (1H, t, J 2.6 Hz), 2.52 (1H, d, J 6.4, 2.6 Hz), 2.53 (1H, dd, J 4.6, 2.6 Hz), 2.72 (1H, br s, OH), 3.42 (3H, s), 4.11 (1H, br s, OH), 4.25–4.36 (1H, m), 4.74 (1H, d, J 6.6 Hz), 4.78 (1H, d, J 6.6 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 22.05 (t), 22.26 (t), 26.13 (q), 30.11 (t), 31.09 (t), 32.25 (t), 35.31 (t), 36.63 (t), 40.59 (t), 44.12 (s), 56.55 (q), 71.04 (d), 75.79 (d), 80.87 (s), 80.99 (s), 83.08 (s), 97.20 (t); HRMS found m/z 296.1985 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_4$ 296.1988.

1-(2-Methoxymethoxypent-4-ynyl)-3 α -methyl-octahydroindene-1,7-diol (**6**) : A mixture of triol **10** (131 mg, 0.52 mmol), chloromethyl methyl ether (0.08 ml, 1.06 mmol), diisopropyl ethylamine (1.0 ml) and anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (15 ml) was stirred at ambient temperature overnight (*ca.* 10 h). It was then poured into water and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (4 : 1, hexanes/ EtOAc), affording methoxy methyl ether **6** (143 mg, 93%) : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.18 (3H, s), 1.19–1.42 (5H, complex), 1.50–1.61 (3H, complex), 1.63–1.70 (1H, m), 1.72–1.89 (3H, complex), 1.93–2.08 (2H, complex), 2.05 (1H, t, J 2.6 Hz), 2.54 (2H, dd, J 5.3, 2.6 Hz), 3.28 (1H, br s, OH), 3.46 (3H, s), 4.08–4.14 (1H, m), 4.37 (1H, br s, OH), 4.74 (1H, d, J 9.9 Hz), 4.82 (1H, d, J 9.9 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 22.14 (t), 22.26 (t), 25.60 (t), 26.25 (q), 31.26 (t), 32.56 (t), 34.83 (t), 35.46 (t), 39.60 (t), 44.09 (s), 56.94 (q), 71.32 (d), 75.52 (d), 80.21 (s), 80.47 (s), 83.94 (s), 96.28 (t); HRMS found m/z 296.1986 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{28}\text{O}_4$ 296.1988.

2-(5-Methoxymethoxy-3-oxo-oct-7-ynyl)-2-methylcy-

clohexanone (7) : A mixture of methoxy methyl ether 5 (26 mg, 0.088 mmol), PDC (333 mg, 0.885 mmol) and anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (5 ml) was stirred at ambient temperature for 4 h. It was then poured into water and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (4 : 1, hexanes/ EtOAc), affording diketone 7 (26 mg, quant.) : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.08 (3H, s), 1.60–1.93 (7H, complex), 1.98–2.04 (1H, m), 2.05 (1H, t, J 2.7 Hz), 2.30 (1H, ddd, J 17.5, 10.9, 5.0 Hz), 2.38 (2H, t, J 6.2 Hz), 2.50 (1H, ddd, J 17.5, 10.8, 5.2 Hz), 2.52–2.56 (2H, complex), 2.76 (1H, dd, J 16.8, 4.8 Hz), 2.85 (1H, dd, J 16.8, 7.7 Hz), 3.38 (3H, s), 4.19–4.25 (1H, m), 4.68 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz), 4.72 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 21.38 (t), 23.04 (q), 25.04 (t), 27.83 (t), 31.22 (t), 38.95 (t), 39.19 (t), 39.88 (t), 47.45 (t), 48.20 (s), 56.12 (q), 71.17 (d), 72.37 (d), 80.57 (s), 96.80 (t), 208.57 (s), 215.99 (s); HRMS found m/z 294.1837 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4$ 294.1831.

2-(5-Methoxymethoxy-3-oxo-oct-7-ynyl)-2-methylcyclohexanone (8) : A mixture of methoxy methyl ether 6 (26 mg, 0.088 mmol), PDC (333 mg, 0.885 mmol) and anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (5 ml) was stirred at ambient temperature for 4 h. It was then poured into water and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (4 : 1, hexanes/ EtOAc), affording diketone 8 (26 mg, quant.) : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.08 (3H, s), 1.58–1.93 (7H, complex), 2.00–2.03 (1H, m), 2.05 (1H, t, J 2.7 Hz), 2.26–2.39 (3H, complex), 2.46–2.54 (3H, complex), 2.75 (1H, dd, J 16.5, 4.7 Hz), 2.90 (1H, dd, J 16.5, 7.8 Hz), 3.39 (3H, s), 4.19–4.26 (1H, m), 4.68 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz), 4.72 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 21.39 (t), 22.99 (q), 25.05 (t), 27.82 (t), 31.24 (t), 38.97 (t), 39.20 (t), 39.95 (t), 47.47 (t), 48.18 (s), 56.12 (q), 71.16 (d), 72.37 (d), 80.57 (s), 96.82 (t), 208.56 (s), 216.03 (s); HRMS found m/z 294.1835 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_4$ 294.1831.

2-(5-Hydroxy-3-oxo-oct-7-ynyl)-2-methylcyclohexanone (11) from triol 9 : A mixture of triol 9 (25 mg, 0.099 mmol), PDC (373 mg, 0.992 mmol) and anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (7 ml) was stirred at ambient temperature for 4 h. It was then poured into water and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (4 : 1 hexanes/ EtOAc), affording diketone 11 (25 mg, quant.) : ^1H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 1.08 (3H, s), 1.62–1.88 (7H, com-

plex), 1.99–2.06 (1H, m), 2.08 (1H, t, J 2.7 Hz), 2.28–2.52 (6H, complex), 2.67 (1H, dd, J 17.5, 8.7 Hz), 2.81 (1H, dd, J 17.5, 3.3 Hz), 3.16 (1H, br d, J 3.7 Hz, OH), 4.17–4.27 (1H, m); ^{13}C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl_3) δ 21.39 (t), 23.02 (q), 26.58 (t), 27.77 (t), 31.32 (t), 38.78 (t), 39.21 (t), 39.91 (t), 48.10 (t), 48.11 (s), 66.49 (d), 71.44 (d), 80.54 (s), 211.36 (s), 216.05 (s); HRMS found m/z 250.1573 (M^+); calcd. for $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$ 250.1569.

2-(5-Hydroxy-3-oxo-oct-7-ynyl)-2-methylcyclohexanone (11) from triol 10 : A mixture of triol 10 (25 mg, 0.099 mmol), PDC (373 mg, 0.992 mmol) and anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (7 ml) was stirred at ambient temperature for 4 h. It was then poured into water and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (4 : 1, hexanes/ EtOAc), affording diketone 11 (23 mg, 91%).

2-(5-Methoxymethoxy-3-oxo-oct-7-ynyl)-2-methylcyclohexanone (8) from diketone 11 : A mixture of triol 11 (25 mg, 0.099 mmol), chloromethyl methyl ether (0.02 ml, 0.27 mmol), diisopropyl ethylamine (0.3 ml) and anhydrous CH_2Cl_2 (5 ml) was stirred at ambient temperature for 15 h. It was then poured into water and extracted with Et_2O (twice). The combined ethereal extracts was washed with brine. After drying (Na_2SO_4) and concentrating, the residue was purified by flash chromatography on silica gel (4 : 1, hexanes/ EtOAc), affording methoxy methyl ether 8 (30 mg, quant.).

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9. The (S)- and (R)-MTPA esters 12 were prepared in quantitative yield by reaction of diketone carbinol 11 with MTPA chloride and DMAP in methylene chloride, rt, 4 h,

